

Genetic Diversity among Tropical Maize (*Zea mays. L*) Inbred Lines for Yield Improvement using SSR and Phenotypic Markers

Akinyosoye, S.T^{1*}, Adebayo, R.J², Balogun, M.O², Fafemi, T.O¹, Sheu, H.T¹

¹Institute of Agricultural Research and Training, Obafemi Awolowo University, Moor Plantation, P.M.B. 5029, Ibadan, Nigeria

²Department of Crop Protection and Environmental Biology, University of Ibadan, Ibadan, Nigeria

Abstract

Maize is an essential food crop in sub-Saharan Africa, however, low yield recorded in Nigeria compared to other African countries like South Africa, could be due to several factors such as expensive fertilizer, low-quality seeds, and poor soil-fertility. This study investigated genetic parameters with the aim of identifying promising inbreds for the development of high-yielding hybrids. Seven maize inbreds were screened using thirteen simple sequence repeat (SSR) markers. The inbreds were assessed under field conditions for seed yield (SY) and various agronomic traits across the early and late cropping seasons of 2024. The results obtained revealed that four SSR-markers (UMC-1066, BNGL-1754, PHI-125, and BNGL-137) had polymorphic information content ($PIC \geq 0.5$) with mean moderate genetic distance (0.6), indicating that moderate genetic diversity existed among the inbreds. Both markers clustered inbreds into different heterotic groups, and consistently identified TZEE-W-POP-STR-C5 as an outstanding candidate. Genotypic, seasons and their interaction were significant for SY and most characters. Inbreds evaluated in early season had better performance than late season for SY, and most traits. The phenotypic coefficient of variation (PCV) was greater than the genotypic coefficient of variation (GCV) for most traits. Heritability coupled with genetic advance were high in SY, and many of the traits, suggesting additive gene effect governed these characters. The two PCA responsible for 99.71% of the variation. Thus, SY, DS, plant, and ear heights (PH, EH), kernels/row (NKPR) and kernel-rows/ear (NKRPE) were the major contributors to the total variation. Therefore, inbred TZEE-W-POP-STR-C5 had highest SY and best performance, making it a promising candidate for improving maize hybrids through heterosis.

Keywords: Maize inbred lines, SSR-based genetic distance, Principal component analysis, Heritability

*Corresponding Author: stakinyosoye@gmail.com

Introduction

Maize (*Zea mays*) is a member of the *Poaceae* family, and it is an annual plant. Globally, it is the 3rd utmost vital cereal apart from rice and wheat (FAOSTAT, 2021) and a chief staple food in sub-Saharan Africa and Latin America with over 1.2 billion people depending on it (IITA, 2009). Maize is important in developing nations, as it assists in reducing current food inadequacy and reduce poverty because it is inexpensive than other cereals including millet, wheat, and rice (Olaniyan, 2015). Additionally, maize is a chief source of food for human, livestock, and industries (breweries) (Olakojo, 2001).

Globally, it is cultivated on approximately 201.1 million ha, with 1.16 billion tons as seed production record and 5.77 t ha⁻¹ as average seed yield (USDA, 2024). In contrast, Africa's maize production stands at roughly 67.69 million tons, derived from 23.45 million ha, and with an average grain yield of 3.1 t ha⁻¹ (USDA, 2024). Consequently, Africa contributes about 5.83% of global maize production and accounts for 11.66% of the total area under maize cultivation. South Africa has highest grain yield (5.81 t ha⁻¹) in SSA, whereas other countries including Nigeria (2.23 t/ha), Malawi (2.05 t ha⁻¹)

¹), Kenya (1.43 t ha⁻¹) and Zimbabwe (1.45 t ha⁻¹) among others, with low yield (USDA, 2024). The low yield recorded in most countries in SSA including Nigeria could be attributed to many factors including but not limited to factors such as expensive fertilizer, low-quality seeds, poor soil-fertility, and poor funding (Oikeh and Horst, 2001), and the increasing incidence of new strains of pests (Badu-Apraku et al., 2014b). Breeders and Geneticists therefore need to explore genetic diversity among inbreds to identify the promising ones for the development of improved maize hybrids to foster food security in SSA.

Phenotypic characterization is important as it helps researchers to improve the use, genetic resources conservation and assists during selection of desired traits (Zannou *et al.*, 2008; Akinyosoye, 2022). As a result, this approach is inexpensive, dependable, and simple to find traits that contribute to or differentiate across breeding lines. Scientists have already characterized germplasm according to their pedigrees, genetic make-up, and contributions of traits to total variations using statistical approaches including principal components (PCA) and cluster analyses (Agbeleye et al., 2020; Akinyosoye et al., 2025). They were employed to ascertain the degree of phenotypic variability in the germplasm of African yam beans, soybeans, peas, alfalfa, mungbean, and maize (Agbeleye et al., 2020; Akinyosoye et al., 2025). The degree of genetic diversity for a character in a population and its heritability is both vital to the achievement of a crop improvement program (Bello et al., 2010; Hussain et al., 2011). The genotypic and phenotypic coefficients of variation (GCV and PCV) can be used to measure diversity in any population (Pratap *et al.*, 2014; Onyia *et al.*,

2017). While PCV comprises genetic and environmental influences, only genetic elements are heritable, while GCV, also known as breeding value, and GCV is only portion that can be inherited (Triveni et al., 2014). Thus, studies on the genetic estimates would help breeders to allocate materials required to ably opt for traits of interest to quickly attain a significant level of genetic gain (Smalley et al., 2004).

Recent advances in DNA-based molecular markers, have significantly improved the accuracy and speed of genetic analysis (Srivastava *et al.*, 2018; Akinyosoye et al., 2023). SSR markers are particularly valuable for studying genetic diversity in maize because of high polymorphism, co-dominance nature, genome-wider coverage, and reproducibility (Gupta and Varshney, 2000; Varshney *et al.*, 2005). SSRs are especially useful in categorizing genotypes into distinct heterotic groups (Reif *et al.*, 2003; Makumbi *et al.*, 2011), compared to phenotypic, biochemical, and pedigree information, molecular markers offer more precise estimations of genetic variation (Gupta *et al.*, 2019). This work aimed to evaluate genetic variability in maize lines using genotypic (SSR) and phenotypic markers; identify promising maize lines for yield improvement; and estimate genetic parameters.

Materials and Methods

Genetic materials

Seven inbred lines of white maize, including extra-early and early maturing maize developed by International Institute of Tropical Agriculture (IITA) for tropical climate were utilized in this research work as genetic materials (Table 1).

Table 1: Pedigrees of tropical maize lines

Entry No	Inbred lines	Pedigree
P1	TZEEI-60	TZEE-Y SR BC1 × 9450STR S6 Inb 3B
P2	TZEEI-29	TZEE-W SR BC5 x 1368 STR S7 Inb.27
P3	TZEEI-28	NA
P4	TZEEI-15	TZEE-W Pop x LDS6(Set A) Inb.44
P5	TZEI-7	WEC STR S7 Inb 12
P6	TZEI-1	TZEE-W SR BC5 3 1368 STR S7 INB 35
P7	TZEE-W-POP-STR-C5	TZEE-W-POP STR Extra

Genotyping of maize inbred lines

Seven maize lines were planted in the screen house of the Institute of Agricultural Research and Training (IAR&T), Ibadan, Nigeria. At two weeks after planting, fresh leaf samples were

collected, labeled in polyethylene nylon bags, and stored in an ice bucket.

DNA extraction was performed on leaf samples of maize lines based on Sodium Dodecyl Sulfate (SDS) protocol (Sika *et al.*, 2015). In this method, approximately 1 g of leaves tissue were processed using an SDS buffer containing 150 mM NaCl, 20 g/L SDS, 25 mM EDTA, 100 mM Tris-HCl at 8.0 pH to get quality product. The homogenate incubated at 65°C for 20 minutes, cooled, and treated with 200 µL of 5 M potassium acetate, then placed on ice. Protein and lipid removal was done using 500 µL chloroform: isoamyl alcohol (24:1), and centrifugation. DNA was precipitated with 500 µL isopropanol at -20°C, rinsed with ethanol (70%), coupled with air-drying and, re-suspension in 60 µL TE buffer, and treated with 2 µL RNase (37°C) for between 30 and 40 minutes. DNA concentration was directly measured in nanograms per microliter (ng/µL), and quality of DNA was assessed using absorbance ratio at wavelengths of 260 nm and 280 nm ($A_{260/280}$). A ratio between 1.8 and 2.0 indicated high-purity DNA. Ratios below 1.8 suggested possible protein contamination, whereas values above 2.0 indicated the existence of impurities including phenol or chloroform (Akinyosoye *et al.*, 2023).

The extracted DNA served as a substrate for polymerase chain reaction (PCR) amplification by using selected simple sequence repeat (SSRs). Although, thirteen SSR markers were initially optimized, eight (BNGL 137, BNGL 1165, BNGL 119, BNGL 1754, PHI 067, PHI 125, UMC 1066, and UMC 1614) were finally selected for the study due to their polymorphism. PCR was performed by using a 25 µL reaction mixture consisting of 2 µL DNA template, 2 µL of 10 µM primer, 8.5 µL nuclease-free water, 12.5 µL of Taq 2X Master Mix (New England Biolabs, M0270). The thermal cycling protocol based on Senior *et al.* (1998) procedures: 94°C (initial denaturation) for 5 minutes, followed by final denaturation for 40 cycles (94°C) for 30 seconds, 55°C (annealing) for 30 seconds, and 72°C (extension) for 45 seconds. The reaction concluded by final extension (72°C) for 7 minutes, and then kept (10°C). The products from PCR were resolved on a 1% (w/v) metaphor-agarose stained with EZ vision DNA stain and visualized under UV transilluminator. Band patterns were scored in binary format, with '1' signifying the existence and '0' signifying the absence of a band.

Phenotyping of inbred lines

The field trial was carried out in 2024 during both early and late cropping seasons at the Institute (IAR&T) in the Forest-Savanna transition zone (7.38°N, 3.84°E; elevation 160 m) with Ferric Lixisols as the major soil type. The field was ploughed and harrowed for proper tilth and laid out in a randomized complete block design (RCBD) with three replicates. Two seeds per inbred line were planted on 5 m single-row plots at 75 cm × 50 cm spacing. Standard agronomic practices and fertilizer recommendations following IAR&T (2010) protocol. Samples of soil were collected from a depth between 0 and 15 cm before planting in each season and analyzed using the Chapman and Pratt (2001) method at the University of Ibadan's Agronomy Laboratory. Fertilizer application included NPK with 60 kg P/ha, 60 kg K/ha, and 60 kg N/ha at two weeks after planting (2WAP) while Urea with 60 kg N/ha was administered at 4WAP. To manage *Spodoptera frugiperda* (armyworm) infestation, a combined insecticide formulation containing 50g per liter (Lambda-cyhalothrin) as well as 100g per liter (Chlorantraniliprole), which was applied as recommended by the manufacturer. Agronomic data collected included days to 50% anthesis (DTA) and silking (DS), plant and ear heights (PH, EH) (measured from five competitive plants at maturity), ear length (EL) and diameter (ED) (measured from five random ears), kernel rows/ear (NRPE), and kernels/row (NKPR). Ear aspect was visually rated on a 1–5 scale based on ear quality (Olakojo and Olaoye, 2005), while ear rot was assessed using a 1–5 severity rating (Horsfall and Barratt, 1945) and seed yield was determined (Badu-Apraku *et al.*, 2012).

Data analyses

For genotyping, DNA molecular analysis was carried out using Power Marker (version: 3.25). The genetic distances in maize inbred lines were computed and cluster analysis was performed to visualize genetic relationships through a dendrogram, whose accuracy was validated using cophenetic correlation.

For phenotyping, ANOVA for yield and other traits was analyzed using the Statistical Tool for Agricultural Research v2.0.1. Variance components, including genotypic, and phenotypic coefficient of variations (GCV, PCV) were estimated using expected mean squares from ANOVA for each trait (Hallauer and Miranda, 1988) and rated as low (< 10%),

moderate (10 - 20%), or high (> 20%) (Saha *et al.* (2019). The heritability in broad sense was determined as the proportion of genotypic to phenotypic variance and categorized as low (< 40%), moderate (40 - 59%), high (60 - 79%), or very high (> 80%) (Singh, 2001). Genetic advance as a percentage of mean (GAM) was determined (Johnson, 1955) and interpreted as low (less than 10%), moderate (10 - 20%), or high (> 20%). Principal component (PC) analysis was performed to recognize major characters contributing to variation among maize inbred lines. Axes having Eigen values ≥ 1 were selected, while traits with loading values ≥ 0.6 were recognized as major contributors to total variability (Matus *et al.*, 1999). Squared Euclidean distance using Hierarchical clustering was used to group the inbreds to produce dendrogram by using PAST software (version 2.17), while cophenetic correlation was assessed used to confirm dendrogram's goodness of fit.

Results

Genetic diversity in maize inbreds using genotypic marker.

The results obtained based on SSR markers revealed that 8 polymorphic markers had overall 24 alleles, and varied from 2 (BNGL 1165, BNGL 119, PHI 067, and UMC 1614) to 3 (BNG L 137, BNGL 1754, PHI 125 and UMC 1066) alleles per locus, and had mean of 2.5. PIC values varied from 0.21 (UMC 1614) to 0.58 (BNG L 137) with mean of 0.43 (Table 2). A significant and positive relationship existed between allele numbers/primer with PIC ($r=0.88^{**}$).

Genetic distance among inbred lines varied from 0.25 (TZE1 1 vs TZEI 29) to 0.75 (TZEI 7 vs TZEI 1, TZEI 7 vs TZEI-W-POP-STRC5, TZEI 7 vs TZEI 28, TZEI 7 vs TZEI 15) with mean of 0.60 (Table 3). Maize lines were clustered into three groups with first cluster having only inbred line TZEI-W-POP-STRC5, while second cluster had two inbred lines TZEI 7 and TZEI 60 and third cluster contained four inbred lines TZEI 1, TZEI 29, TZEI 28 and TZEI 15 (Figure 1). The cophenetic correlation coefficient was high ($r_{cop} = 0.82$).

Table 2: Genetic information on eight polymorphic SSR markers used

Marker	Major allele frequency	Allele number	Gene diversity	PIC
BNG L 137	0.43	3.00	0.65	0.58
BNGL 1165	0.57	2.00	0.49	0.37
BNGL 119	0.57	2.00	0.49	0.37
BNGL 1754	0.43	3.00	0.61	0.53
PHI 067	0.57	2.00	0.49	0.37
PHI 125	0.57	3.00	0.57	0.50
UMC 1066	0.57	3.00	0.57	0.50
UMC 1614	0.86	2.00	0.24	0.21
Mean	0.57	2.50	0.52	0.43

Table 3: Genotypic estimates of genetic distance in maize lines using SSR markers

Inbred lines	TZE1-7	TZEI-1	TZEI-60	TZEI-29	TZEI-W-POP-STRC5	TZEI-28	TZEI-15
TZE1-7	1	0.75	0.38	0.50	0.75	0.75	0.75
TZEI-1		1	0.63	0.25	0.63	0.63	0.63
TZEI-60			1	0.63	0.63	0.63	0.63
TZEI-29				1	0.75	0.63	0.38
TZEI-W-POP-STR-C5					1	0.75	0.63
TZEI-28						1	0.38
TZEI-15							1

P1: TZEI 7, P2: TZEI 1, P3: TZEI 60, P4: TZEI 29, P5: TZEI-W-POP-STRC5, P6: TZEI 28, P7: TZEI 15

Figure 1: Dendrogram of genetic association of maize lines using genotypic (SSR) markers

Nutrient status, and rainfall at the experimental site

The results of soil samples collected revealed that sand had highest proportion (80%), whereas proportions of clay along with silt were 9% and 11%, respectively, while pH was 6.71, which was within the recommended range for maize production. The results obtained from soil chemical analysis indicated that total nitrogen (N) was very low (<0.20%), coupled with Phosphorus (<15.00), Potassium (<0.20), and organic carbon (<4.00), when compared with the recommended standard (Table 4). The

result of rainfall patterns obtained during the evaluation revealed that the early season (June – August) received higher mean rainfall (212.67 mm) than the late season (September – November) with rainfall of 137.67 mm. The day temperature ranged from 24.13°C (early season) to 25.07°C (late season) (Table 5). Severe rain cessation was experienced during the late season evaluation especially in November, which coincided with the reproductive stage (anthesis, silking and seed filling), which adversely affected crop performance.

Table 4: Soil nutrient profile of the experimental sites in Ibadan 2024

Parameter	Experimental site	Landon (1991)	
Chemical characteristics		High	Low
PH [H ₂ O]	6.71	>6.5	<5.8
%Organic carbon	0.16	>10	<4
%Total nitrogen	0.08	>0.5	<0.2
Available phosphorus	4.48	>50	<15
Ca (cmol/kg)	1.27	>10	<4
Mg (cmol/kg)	0.30	>4	<0.5
K (cmol/kg)	0.16	>0.6	<0.2
Na (cmol/kg)	0.10	>1	<1
Physical characteristics			
Sand%	80		

Silt%	11
Clay%	9

Table 5: Monthly mean rainfall and temperature at the experimental site in Ibadan in 2024

SN	Month	Rainfall (mm)	Temperature (°C)
1	January	17	27.32
2	February	30	27.9
3	March	67	27.7
4	April	114	26.9
5	May	176	25.9
6	June	214	24.6
7	July	218	24
8	August	206	23.8
9	September	215	24.2
10	October	159	24.9
11	November	39	26.1
12	December	12	26.9
	Mean of early season	212.67	24.13
	Mean of late season	137.67	25.07

Extracted from database of Nigerian Metrological Agency, climate data for Ibadan, Nigeria

Analysis of variance and performance of tropical maize inbreds for agronomic traits

The results obtained from ANOVA across seasons showed that genotypic (G), and seasonal (S) effects were significant for traits such as seed yield (SY), DTA, DS, PH, ED, NRPE and NKPR. The interaction $G \times S$ showed significant effect for all characters except plant and ear heights, ear aspect and ear rot (Table 6). Substantial variation existed among the inbreds with coefficients of variation (CV) ranging from 1.21% for DS in early season to 47.67% for ear rot in late season. The inbreds evaluated in early season (575.16 kg/ha) out yielded those evaluated in late season (217.86 kg/ha). Inbred lines evaluated in early season reached DTA and DS with mean of 52 and 55 days after planting (DAP), respectively earlier than the those evaluated in late season with an average of 53 for DTA and 57 DS. In addition, inbreds evaluated in early season were taller than those evaluated in late season by 5.67 cm

and 2.26 cm for PH and EH, respectively. Similarly, inbreds evaluated in early season had better performance than late season in major yield components such ED, and NRPE (Table 7).

Across seasons, CV ranged from 2.21% for DS to 58.79% for ear rot. Mean performance of inbreds assessed revealed that the seed yield ranged from 241.83 kg ha⁻¹ (TZEI 1) to 819.17 kg ha⁻¹ (TZEE-W-POP-STR-C5). The inbred lines had grand mean of 396.51 kg ha⁻¹ across two seasons. The extra-early maturing inbred lines reached 50% anthesis within 51-52 DAP, while early maturing inbreds attained 50% anthesis within 54-55 DAP. Similarly, extra-early maturing lines reached 50% silking within 54-55 DAP, whereas early maturing lines attained silking within 57-58 DAP (Table 8).

Table 6: Mean squares for agronomic characters of tropical maize inbreds assessed in both early and late seasons in Ibadan, 2024

SOV	Df	SY	DTA	DS	PH	EH	EL	ED	NRPE	NKPR	EAS	EROT
Season (S)	1	1340456.18	27.52	42.00	337.17	3392.11	53.70	8.46	179.55	402.20	1.17	0.72
Rep within S	2	38645.86	2.26	0.69	542.35	5052.65	10.76	0.78	2.98	46.06	0.83	3.67
Lines (L)	6	220711.42	17.87	16.65	1877.82	429.21	7.81	0.37	13.90	43.10	0.78	0.76
S × L	6	2285643.52	14.19	11.44	0.00	41.04	13.54	0.32	16.49	62.26	0.51	1.07
Pooled Error	24	15521.19	3.57	1.52	62.00	64.25	2.05	0.12	0.45	10.11	0.33	1.57

LSD	209.94	3.18	2.08	14.60	14.86	3.75	0.58	1.13	5.36	1.29
-----	--------	------	------	-------	-------	------	------	------	------	------

SY= grain yield, DTA = 50%anthesis, DS= 50%silking, PH= plant height, EH= ear height (cm), EL and ED = ear length and diameter (cm), NRPE and NKPR = kernels' rows/ear, and kernels/row

Table 7: Mean of maize lines assessed for agronomic characters in both early and late seasons in Ibadan in 2024

Lines	SY	DTA	DS	PH	EH	EL	ED	NRPE	NKPR	EAS	EROT
Early season											
TZEE-W-PO-STRC5	1464.05	48.00c	52.00c	140.23a	80.27a	7.59ab	3.90a	14.50b	13.70a	2.00a	1.33a
TZEEI-15	339.87b	52.00ab	55.00b	96.15c	55.28a	6.79ab	3.60a	17.50a	13.70a	2.83a	1.33a
TZEEI-28	392.16b	51.67ab	53.33c	109.23bc	65.13a	7.09ab	3.60a	14.00b	10.70a	3.33a	2.50a
TZEEI-29	470.59b	48.67bc	52.00c	138.90a	75.70a	5.89ab	3.10a	10.00c	10.70a	2.67a	1.50a
TZEI-1	287.58b	54.00a	57.00a	129.10ab	79.17a	9.29ab	3.40a	17.50a	12.20a	3.17a	2.50a
TZEI-60	601.31b	56.00a	58.67a	102.33c	66.80a	8.09ab	3.20a	15.50b	9.70a	3.00a	2.50a
TZEI-7	470.59b	53.00ab	56.67a	113.00bc	63.70a	4.89b	3.30a	10.50c	7.70a	3.33a	2.33a
Mean	575.16	51.90	54.95	118.42	69.44	8.22	2.99	14.21	14.29	2.90	2.13
Std Error	123.02	1.78	0.54	6.43	8.19	0.30	0.06	0.63	0.45	0.55	2.00
CV(%)	26.20	4.07	1.21	6.65	14.44	17.41	11.40	5.53	22.25	23.05	2.13
Late season											
TZEE-W-PO-STRC5	174.30a	54.33a	58.00a	134.57a	53.37ab	11.53a	2.42a	8.80b	20.73ab	2.67a	2.33a
TZEEI-15	239.65a	55.00a	58.33a	90.48c	38.80c	5.64c	2.08b	9.58ab	9.52d	2.00b	3.00a
TZEEI-28	326.80a	50.67a	53.67b	103.57bc	45.53bc	11.64a	3.23a	10.91a	25.07a	3.33a	1.67a
TZEEI-29	217.86a	53.33a	57.00a	133.23a	53.33ab	10.33a	2.41a	9.93ab	19.28ab	2.67a	1.67a
TZEI-1	196.08a	54.67a	57.67a	1123.43a	63.23a	8.16ab	2.58a	11.23a	15.40bc	2.67a	2.83a
TZEI-60	108.93a	54.67a	57.67a	96.67c	58.20ab	7.67bc	2.21b	9.07b	11.50cd	2.00b	2.88a
TZEI-7	261.44a	52.00a	56.33a	107.33bc	45.77bc	10.47a	2.90a	11.03a	20.22ab	2.67a	2.00a
Mean	217.86	53.52	56.95	112.75	51.46	3.02	2.55	10.08	11.20	2.57	2.26
Std Error	48.82	1.78	1.32	6.43	4.32	1.65	0.39	0.78	3.67	0.37	0.88
CV (%)	41.92	4.07	2.83	6.98	10.27	21.64	18.96	9.42	25.86	17.67	47.67

Std Error and CV% = Standard error and percentage coefficient of variation respectively. SY= grain yield, DTA = 50%anthesis, DS= 50%silking, PH= plant height, EH= ear height (cm), EL and ED = ear length and diameter (cm), NRPE and NKPR = kernels' rows/ear, and kernels/row

Table 8: Mean of maize lines assessed for agronomic characters across seasons in Ibadan, 2024

Lines	SY	DTA	DS	PH	EH	EL	ED	NRPE	NKPR	EAS	EROT
TZEE-W- PO- STRC5	819.17	51.17	55.00	137.40	67.82	9.56	3.16	1.65	17.22	2.33	1.83
TZEEI-15	239.76	51.50	56.67	93.32	47.04	6.21	2.84	13.54	11.61	2.42	2.17
TZEEI-28	359.48	51.17	53.50	109.40	55.33	9.37	3.41	12.46	17.88	3.33	2.08
TZEEI-29	344.23	51.00	54.50	136.07	64.52	8.11	2.75	9.97	14.99	2.67	1.58
TZEI-1	241.83	54.33	57.33	126.27	71.20	7.88	2.99	14.37	13.80	2.92	2.67
TZEI-60	355.12	55.33	58.17	99.50	62.50	7.68	2.71	12.28	10.60	2.50	2.42
TZEI 7	366.01	52.50	56.50	110.17	54.73	3.16	3.10	10.76	13.96	3.00	2.17
Mean	389.37	52.43	55.95	116.02	60.45	7.42	2.99	10.72	14.29	2.74	2.13
CV%	31.42	3.58	2.21	6.81	13.26	17.41	11.40	5.53	22.25	20.90	58.79

SY= grain yield, DTA = 50%anthesis, DS= 50%silking, PH= plant height, EH= ear height (cm), EL and ED = ear length and diameter (cm), NRPE and NKPR = kernels' rows/ear, and kernels/row

Variance and heritability estimate of maize inbreds for agronomic traits

Genotypic, phenotypic, and environmental variances, heritability and GAM are presented in Tables 9. The results obtained showed that magnitude of phenotypic variances was greater than genotypic variances for yield and others measured. PCV ranged from 4.58% for DS to 73.06% for yield, whereas GCV varied from 4.01% for DS to 123.12% for ear rot. The PCV was greater than GCV for all traits measured except ED, and ear rot. On the other hand, heritability estimates in broad sense revealed that very high heritability was recorded in some traits including seed yield, PH and NRPE (> 80%). High heritability was obtained in DS and EH (60-79%). Moderate heritability was observed in DTA, EH, ED and NKPR (40-59%), while the rest had low heritability estimates (<40%). The GAM revealed that some traits had high GAM (greater than 20%) such as seed yield, EH, NRPE, and NKPR. Some traits such as ear ED, and ear aspect recorded moderate GAM (10-20%), while the rest had low GAM (<10%).

Table 9: Variances and heritability for agronomic characters of maize lines assessed across seasons in Ibadan in 2024

	Genotypic variance	Phenotypic	GCV	PCV	H%	GAM
SY	68396.74	83917.93	65.96	73.06	81.50	122.84
DTA	4.77	8.33	4.14	5.48	57.26	6.47
DAS	5.04	6.56	4.01	4.58	76.84	7.26
PH	605.27	667.27	21.28	22.35	90.71	41.82
EH	121.66	185.90	18.25	22.55	65.44	30.45
EL	1.92	3.96	16.87	24.22	48.52	24.24
ED	0.09	0.20	94.62	14.03	44.07	12.76
NRPE	4.48	4.93	17.43	18.28	90.88	34.27
NKPR	11.00	21.11	23.21	32.15	52.10	34.56
EAS	0.15	0.47	14.29	25.11	32.39	16.78
EROT	0.00	1.57	123.12	72.41	0.00	0.00

GCV and PCV: genotypic and phenotypic coefficient of variation, H: heritability, GAM: genetic advance mean, SY= grain yield, DTA = 50%anthesis, DS= 50%silking, PH= plant height, EH= ear height (cm), EL and ED = ear length and diameter (cm), NRPE and NKPR = kernels' rows/ear, and kernels/row

Principal component analysis and clustering of tropical maize inbred using phenotypic markers

The principal component had seven component axes (Eigen values ≥ 1) (Table 10). Seven selected PCs responsible for 99.99% of total variation. Two principal components (PC 1 and PC 2) responsible for 99.71% of total variation, with PC 1 and PC 2 responsible for 99.11% and 0.60%, respectively. PC 1 associated mainly with yield, while PC 2 associated with only EH. PC3, PC4 and PC5 accounted for 0.25%, 0.02% and 0.01% of total variation, where they were associated with PH, NRPE and NKPR, respectively. Also, about 0.01% and 0.001%

contributions to variation were attributed to PC 6 and PC 7, respectively. DTA and DS were associated with PC 6, while only ear rot was associated with PC 7 (Table 10). In addition, clustering analysis delineated the lines into two major clusters, where first cluster contained only one inbred line TZEE-W-POP-STRC5, while second cluster divided lines into two sets. The set I comprised of four inbreds TZEEI 29, TZEEI 60, TZEI 7 and TZEEI 28, while second set contained two inbred lines TZEEI 15 and TZEI 1 (Figure 2). The cophenetic correlation (r_{cop}) as a measure of dendrogram's goodness of fit based on agronomic data was 0.99.

Table 10: Principal components (PCs) for agronomic characters of maize lines

Characters	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
SY	0.99*	0.001	-0.02	0.00	-0.003	0.01	-0.003
DTA	-0.004	0.003	-0.05	-0.23	0.14	0.67*	-0.21
DS	-0.004	0.01	-0.03	-0.18	0.05	0.64*	0.64
PH	0.02	0.28	0.96*	-0.03	0.03	0.04	-0.01
EH	-0.004	0.95*	-0.28	-0.13	-0.01	-0.06	0.00
EL	-0.001	0.07	-0.01	0.31	0.17	0.20	0.03
ED	0.001	0.004	0.002	0.02	0.12	-0.12	0.01
NRPE	0.003	-0.01	-0.02	-0.03	0.97*	-0.15	0.00
NKPR	-0.002	0.13	-0.02	0.89*	0.02	0.23	0.03
EAS	0.00	0.003	0.002	0.02	0.07	-0.03	0.32

EROT	0.00	-0.003	0.003	-0.08	-0.01	0.11	0.52
Eigen values	119695.00	727.64	303.58	27.82	8.28	7.28	1.39
% variation	99.11	0.60	0.25	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.00
Cumulative	99.11	99.71	99.96	99.98	99.99	100.00	100.00

SY= grain yield, DTA = 50%anthesis, DS= 50%silking, PH= plant height, EH= ear height (cm), EL and ED = ear length and diameter (cm), NRPE and NKPR = kernels' rows/ear, and kernels/row

Figure 2: Dendrogram of maize inbreds for phenotypic traits based on squared Euclidean distance

Discussion

Genetic diversity in maize genotypes using genotypic and phenotypic markers has been reported, which is crucial in strengthening breeding programs for the identification and selection of promising parents from the gene pools for the development of improved hybrids through exploitation of heterosis (Akinyosoye *et al.*, 2023). Thus, identification of promising parents or inbred lines would assist breeders in development of improved hybrids for the important traits especially, improved yield, resilience to climate change, nutritional quality.

High polymorphic information content (PIC) obtained in four SSR primers UMC 1066, BNGL 1754, PHI 125, and BNGL 137 with PIC values (≥ 0.5), suggests that these primers were highly informative and effective for analyzing genetic variability or diversity in maize inbreds (Sharma *et al.*, 2009). Thus, high PIC values observed in these primers make them important for

discriminating between genotypes, and detecting allelic variation, which might be utilized in marker-assisted breeding (MAB) programs aims at improving them for resilience and high yield. In this study, average alleles number/locus (2.5) obtained is very near to figures reported by others with the varied from 2.5 to 2.86 alleles/locus (Rupp *et al.*, 2009; Badu-Apraku *et al.*, 2013; Lopes *et al.*, 2015; Akinyosoye *et al.*, 2023). The significant and positive association recorded between number of alleles and PIC, indicates that primers with high number of alleles have likelihood to exhibit greater PIC. The result obtained is supported by the findings of Vaz-Patto *et al.* (2004) as well as Akinyosoye *et al.* (2023).

The genetic distance (GD) based on genotypic marker in inbreds revealed an average of 0.6. This suggests the existence of genetic relatedness in the inbreds used in this study, while hybridization among these inbreds have a likelihood of exploitation of heterosis. This result

aligns with the range reported by others for the exploitation of heterosis (Vaz-Patto *et al.*, 2004; Legesse *et al.*, 2007; Dhliwayo *et al.*, 2009; Akinyosoye *et al.*, 2023). Clustering of inbreds based on genotypic markers revealed that inbred lines TZEI 1 vs TZEI 29 were the most closely related, while inbred lines TZEI 7 vs TZEI 1, TZEI 7 vs TZEI-W-POP-STR-C5, TZEI 7 vs TZEI 28, TZEI 7 vs TZEI 15 were the most distantly related. The closeness of TZEI 1 and TZEI 29 may be due to having the same breeding source or obtained from the same gene pool, because both TZEI 1 and TZEI 29 were drawn from the similar gene pool (TZEI-W-SR BC5 × 1368 STR S7), while those inbred lines that were distantly related were drawn from large gene pools of different pedigree.

Although, information obtained using genotypic markers using genotypic markers is more reliable than phenotypic marker based on agronomic data, due to the impact of environments on the phenotypic expression (Vaz-Patto *et al.*, 2004; Legesse *et al.*, 2007), but both markers can complement each other in breeding programs. Clustering of inbreds based on genotypic and phenotypic markers resulted in different heterotic groups. However, both markers consistently identified TZEI-W-POP-STR-C5 as an outlier. It is worthy of note that inbred line TZEI-W-POP-STR-C5 had the highest yield and better performance in most traits. As a result of this, TZEI-W-POP-STR-C5 could serve as a promising parent for introgression of novel traits or genetic variability in breeding programs, particularly for broadening the genetic base or improving heterosis in hybrid combinations. The high cophenetic correlation obtained in both phenotypic and genotypic groupings confirms the reliability and accuracy of the clustering methods used for both phenotypic and genotypic data in this study.

The significant genotypic, seasonal effects and their interaction for most characters, depict that both genetic variability and seasonal differences, and their interactions had a substantial impact on these traits. Golla *et al.* (2018) also reported similar finding with respect to the environmental influence, and planting date on maize yield. In addition, it was reported that differences in yield and its components in maize had been ascribed to variations in climatic conditions (Tripathi *et al.*, 2022; Dhakal *et al.*, 2022). Inbred lines evaluated in early season had better performance than

those evaluated in late season for seed yield, and most of other agronomic traits could be due to the severe rain cessation experienced during the late season especially in November, which coincided with the reproductive stage (anthesis, silking and seed filling), which adversely affected their performance. This result is validated by the findings of others (Jahangirlou *et al.* 2021; Mekonnen *et al.*, 2023) on maize. Hence, the need for strategic planning when engaging in late season planting to prevent huge yield loss as experienced in this study due to erratic rainfall patterns as caused by climate change.

The greater magnitude of PCV compared to GCV for most of the traits in maize in this work, indicates that the phenotypic expression is under the control of both genetic and environmental factors and that environmental conditions play a significant role in the expression of these traits. Thus, findings of others supported these (Kandel *et al.*, 2017; Sharma *et al.*, 2018). The level of heritable variation can only be assessed using heritability estimates and genetic gain (Rao and Rao, 2015). In this work, the high GAM and heritability recorded for seed yield, PH, NKPE, DS and EH, suggests that these traits are predominantly influenced by additive gene action. This indicates that selecting for these traits would be an efficient approach for achieving high genetic gain in maize. According to Krishna *et al.* (2009), traits controlled by additive gene effects typically exhibit both high GAM and heritability, whereas traits influenced by non-additive gene effects may show high heritability but low GAM.

The existence of genotypic variability among the inbred lines based on agronomic traits was further substantiated using principal components (PC). The first two PC responsible for 99.71% of total variation with PC1 and PC2 having 99.11% and 0.60%, respectively, which were associated with seed yield and EH. PC values greater than 0.6 were identified as major contributors to total variations as reported by Matus *et al.* (1999). Thus, grain yield, DS, PH, EH, NRPE and NKPR were major contributors to total variations in this work. Thus, agronomic traits identified as major contributors could fast-track efficient selection in maize breeding programs.

Conclusion

Four SSR-markers (UMC-1066, BNGL-1754, PHI-125, and BNGL-137) had PIC ≥ 0.5 with average genetic distance of 0.6, indicating moderate genetic diversity existed among inbreds. Both markers clustered inbreds into different heterotic groups, but consistently identified TZEE-W-POP-STR-C5 as an outlier. Genotypic, seasonal effects and their interaction were significant for seed yield and most of the traits. Inbreds evaluated in early season had better performance than late season for seed yield, and most of the agronomic traits. Magnitude of PCV was greater than GCV for most of the traits. High GAM and heritability were recorded for seed yield, DS, and most of the traits, suggesting that additive gene actions governed these traits. Two principal components (PC 1 and PC 2) responsible for 99.71% of total variation, with PC 1 and PC 2 responsible for 99.11% and 0.60%, respectively. Thus, SY, DS, PH, EH, NKPR and NRPE were the major contributors to total variation. As a result of this, TZEE-W-POP-STR-C5 had highest seed yield and best performance, making it a promising candidate for improving maize hybrids through heterosis.

References

Agbeleye O.A., Akinyosoye S.T., Adetumbi, J.A. 2020. Correlation, path coefficient and principal component analysis of yield components in mung bean [*Vigna radiata* (L.) Wilczek] accessions. *Tropical Agriculture* 97: 212-218.

Akinyosoye S.T., Oladipo M.S., Fafemi T.O., Sheu H.T., Adetumbi J.A. and Mshelmbula B.P. 2025. Genetic estimates of winged bean [*Psophocarpus tetragonolobus* (L.) DC] genotypes for agronomic traits. *Journal of Underutilized Legumes*. 7 (1): 57 – 66

Akinyosoye, S, 2022. Characterization of African Yam Bean (*Sphenostylis stenocarpa*) Mutant Lines using Phenotypic Markers. *Yuzuncu Yil University Journal of Agricultural Sciences*, 32(3): 487-496.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.29133/yyutbd.1115956>

Akinyosoye, S. T., Balogun, M. O. and Olakojo, S. A. 2023. Heterosis of quality protein maize inbred lines for agronomic traits and association with genetic distances based on SSR and phenotypic markers. *Plant Gene* 36 (2): 1-10

Badu-Apraku, B., Asuboah, R. A., Fakorede, M., and Asafo-Adjei, B. 2014a. *Strategies for Sustainable Maize Seed Production in West and Central Africa*. Ibadan: IITA.

Badu-Apraku, B., Fakorede, M. A., and Oyekunle, M. 2014b. Agronomic traits associated with genetic gains in maize yield during three breeding eras in West Africa. *Maydica* 59: 49–57.

Badu-Apraku, B., Fakorede, M.A.B., Menkir, A., Sanogo, D., 2012. Conduct and Management of Maize Field Trials. IITA, Ibadan, Nigeria, p. 59.

Badu-Apraku, B., Oyekunle, M., Akinwale, R.O. and Aderounmu, M. 2013. Combining ability and genetic variability of extra-early white maize inbred lines under stress and non-stress environments. *Crop Science* 53, 9–26.

Bantte, K. and Prasanna, B. M., 2003. Simple sequence repeat polymorphism in quality protein maize (QPM) lines. *Euphytica* 129: 337–344.

Bello, O. B., Abdulmalik, S. Y., Afolabi, M. S. and Ige, S. A. 2010. Correlation and path coefficient analysis of yield and agronomic characters among open OPV and their F₁ Hybrids in a Diallel Cross. *African Journal of Biotechnology* 9(18): 2633-2639.

Chapman, H. D and Pratt, P. F. 2001. *Methods of Analysis for Soils, Plants and Waters*. University of California.

Dhakal, K., Pokhrel, K. R., Baral, B. R., Ayer, D. K. and Joshi, D. 2022. Three-way cross white kernel hybrid maize out-yielded commercial variety tested under two contrasting environments *J. Agric. Food Res.*, 7 (2022).

Dhliwayo, T., Pixley, K., Menkir, A., Warburton, M., 2009. Combining ability, genetic distances, and heterosis of CIMMYT and IITA tropical maize inbred lines. *Crop Sci.* 49(4): 1201-1210

Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, FAOSTAT, 2021. FAOSTAT Database. Rome: FAO; (2021). Available online at: <http://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#home> (accessed February 15, 2021).

- Golla, B., Tadesse, B., Chalsisa, D. and Bayisa, E. 2018. Effect of sowing time and environmental variation on yield of different Maize varieties *Open J. Polit. Sci.*, 3: 41-45, [10.17352/ojps.000014](https://doi.org/10.17352/ojps.000014).
- Gupta, P. K. and Varshney, R. K. 2000. The development and use of microsatellite markers for genetic analysis and plant breeding with emphasis on bread wheat. *Euphytica* 113(3): 163–185.
- Gupta, S., Gopalakrishna, T., Gupta, V., 2019. Molecular markers: an overview and applications in crop improvement. *Agric. Biol. J. N. Am.* 10 (1): 1–12.
- Hallauer, A. and Miranda, J. 1988. Heredity variance: Mating Design Quantitative Genetics in Maize Breeding. 2nd edition, USA: Iowa State University Press, Ames. 45-114.
- Horsfall, J.G. and Barratt, R.W. 1945. An improved grading system for measuring plant diseases. *Phytopathology* 35:655.
- Hussain, N., Khan, M. Y. and Baloch, M. S. 2011. Screening of maize varieties for seed yield at Dera Ismail Khan. *J. Animal and Plant Sci.*, 21(3): 626-628.
- IAR&T. (2010). Institute of Agricultural Research & Training. Farmers' Guide Series 1. No. 4: Guide on Maize Production. Obafemi Awolowo University, Ibadan. 7p.
- International Institute of Tropical Agriculture (IITA) 2009. Research for Development: Cereals and Legume System
- Jahangirlou, M. R., Akbari, G. A., Alahdadi, I., Soufizadeh, S., Kumar, U. and Parsons, D. 2021. Phenotypic traits, grain yield and yield components of maize cultivars under combinations of management practices in semi-arid conditions of Iran *Int. J. Plant Prod.*, 15 (3): 459-471, [10.1007/s42106-021-00151-7](https://doi.org/10.1007/s42106-021-00151-7).
- Johnson, H. N., Robinson, H. F. and Comstock, R. E. 1955. Estimate of genetic and environmental variability in soybean. *Agronomy Journal* 27: 314-318.
- Kandel, B. P., Poudel, A., Sharma, S. and Subedi, M. 2017. Variability studied in yield attributing traits of early maize genotypes in western hill of Nepal. *Nepal. J. Agri. Sci.*, 15: 13-18
- Krishna, D. M., Reddy, D. M., Reddy, K. H. P. and Sudhakar, P. 2009. Character association and interrelationship of yield and quality attributes in rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) *Andhra Agric. J.*, 56 (3): 298-301.
- Legesse, B. W., Myburg, A. A., Pixley, K. V. and Botha, A. M. 2007. Genetic variability of African maize inbred lines revealed by SSR markers. *Hereditas* 144, 10–17.
- Lopes, A. D., Scapim, C. A., Pires, M. F., Machado, S., Mangolin, C. A., Silva, T. A., Cantagali, L. B., Teixeira, F. F. and Mora, F. 2015. Genetic diversity assessed by SSR markers in sweet corn cultivars. *Sci. Agric.* 72 (6), 513–519.
- Makumbi, D., Betran, J. F., Banziger, M. and Ribaut, J. M. 2011. Combining ability, heterosis and genetic diversity in tropical maize under stress and non-stress conditions. *Euphytica* 180: 143-162.
- Matus, I., Gonzales, M. I. and Pozo, A. 1999. Evaluation of phenotypic variation in a Chilean collection of garlic (*Allium sativum* L.) clones using multivariate analysis. *Plant Genetic Resources Newsletter* 117: 31-34.
- Mekonnen, T. W., Biljon, A.V., Ceronio, G. and Labuschagne, M. 2023. Effects of planting date, environments and their interaction on grain yield and quality traits of maize hybrids, *Heliyon* 9(11): e21660, doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.101660.
- Oikeh, S. O. and Horst, W. J. 2001. Agro-physiological responses of tropical maize cultivars to nitrogen fertilization in the moist savanna of West Africa. In: Horst WJ, Schenk MK, Bürkert A, Claassen N, Flessa H, Frommer WB, *et al.*, editors. Plant Nutrition. Dordrecht (The Netherlands): Springer; 2001. p. 804-5.
- Olakojo, S. A. 2001. Effects of some biotic and abiotic factors on maize seed yield in southwestern Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Pure and Applied Science* 15:1045-1050
- Olakojo, S. A. and Olaoye, G. 2005. Combining ability for seed yield, agronomic traits and *Striga*

- lutea* tolerance of maize hybrids under artificial striga infestation. *African Journal of Biotechnology* 4(9): 984 - 988.
- Olaniyan, A. B. 2015. Maize: Panacea for hunger in Nigeria. *African Journal of Plant Science*, 9(3): 155-174
- Onyia, V. N., Okechukwu, E. C., Atugwu, A. I. and Akpan, N. M. 2017. Genetic variability studies on twelve genotypes of rice for growth and yield performance in South Eastern Nigeria. *Notulae Scientia Biologicae* 9(1):110-115.
- Pratap, N., Singh, P. K., Shekhar, R., Soni, S. K. and Mall, A. K. 2014. Genetic variability, character association and diversity analyses for economic traits in rice. *SAARC Journal of Agriculture* 10: 83-94.
- Rao, P. J. M. and Rao, V. T. 2015. Genetic analysis for yield and its components in pigeon pea (*Cajanus cajan* L.) MILL SP) *Int. J. Appl. Biol. Pharmaceut. Technol.*, 6(2): 189-190.
- Reif, J., Melchinger, A., Xia, X., Warburton, M., Hoisington, D., Vasal, S., Srinivasan, G., Bohn, M. and Frisch, M. 2003. Genetic distance based on SSR and heterosis in tropical maize. *Crop Science* 43: 1275-1282.
- Rupp, J., Mangolin, C., Scapim, C. and Machado, M. 2009. Genetic structure and diversity among sweet corn progenies using SSR markers. *Maydica* 54, 125–132.
- Saha, S. R., Hassan, L., Haque, M. A., Islam, M. M. and Rasel, M. 2019. Genetic variability, heritability, correlation and path analyses of yield components in traditional rice landraces. *Journal of Bangladesh Agricultural University* 17(1): 26–32.
- Senior, M., Murphy, J., Goodman, M. and Stuber, C. 1998. Utility of SSR for determining genetic similarity and relationship in maize using an agarose gel system. *Crop Science* 38: 1088 – 1098
- Sharma, M. V., Kantartzi, S. K. and Stewart, J. M. 2009. Molecular variability and polymorphism information content of selected *Gossypium hirsutum* accessions, summaries of Arkansas cotton research. *AAES Res. Ser.* 582: 124–127.
- Sharma, B. K., Sharma, S., Kandel, B. P. and Shrestha, J. 2018. Varietal evaluation of promising maize genotypes. *Azarian J. Agri.*, 5(4):120-124.
- Sika, K.C., Kefela, T., Adoukonou-Sagbadja, H., Ahoton, L., Saidou, A., Baba-Moussa, L., Baptiste, L.J., Kotconi, S.O. and Emma W. Gachomo, E.W. 2015. A simple and efficient genomic DNA extraction protocol for large scale genetic analyses of plant biological systems. *Plant Gene* 1: 43-45. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.plgene.2015.03.001>.
- Singh, B. 2001. Plant Breeding: Principles and Methods. Kalyani Publishers, New Delhi, India. 923p.
- Singh, P. 2015. Genetic distance, heterosis and combing ability studies in maize for predicting F1 hybrid performance. *J. Breed. Genet.* 47 (1): 21–28.
- Smalley, M., Daub, J. and Hallauer, A. 2004. Estimation of heritability in maize by parent-offspring regression. *Maydica*, 49: 221-229.
- Srivastava, P., Srivastava, S. K., Katiyar, P. and Awasthi, A. K., 2018. Comparative analysis of RAPD, ISSR, and AFLP molecular markers for assessment of genetic diversity and population structure of Indian rose accessions. *Biotech* 8(1): 12.
- Statistical Tool for Agricultural Research (STAR, Version: 2.0.1, 2013 - 2020). Rice Research Institute (IRRI). <http://bbi.irri.org>.
- Thapa, S., Rawal, S. and Adhikari, S. 2022. Varietal evaluation of hybrid maize in the summer and winter seasons in terai region of Nepal, *Heliyon* 8 (11) doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2022.e11619.
- Tripathi, M. P., Gautam, D., Koirala, K. B., Shrestha, H. K. and Abdulrahman, B. 2022. Evaluation of pro-vitamin an enriched maize hybrids for fighting hidden hunger in Nepal *J. Agric. Appl. Biol.*, 3:19-27.
- Triveni S., Kumar, A., Dwivedi, S. C. and Vyas, R. P. 2014. Estimate of genetic factors and

correlation analysis in maize. *Plant Archives* 14(1): 19-21.

USDA (United States Department of Agriculture) (2024). World Agricultural Production. Foreign Agricultural Service/USDA, Global Market Analysis. Circular Series WAP 10-24 October 2024. 38p.

Varshney, R.K., Graner, A., Sorrells, M.E., 2005. Genic microsatellite markers in plants: features and applications. *Trends Biotechnol.* 23(1): 48–55.

Vaz-Patto, M. C., Satovic, Z., Pego, S., Feveireiro, P. 2004. Assessing the genetic variability of Portuguese maize germplasm using microsatellite markers. *Euphytica* 137, 63–72.

Zannou, A., Kossou, D.K., Ahanchédé, A., Zoundjihékpon, J., Agbicodo, E., Struik, P.C. and Sanni, A.,2008. Genetic variability of cultivated cowpea in Benin assessed by random amplified polymorphic DNA. *Afr. J. Biotechnol.* 7(24): 4407-4414